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THE USE OF SEMANTIC FORMS OF ADJECTIVE IN T. KAYIPBERGENOV'S "MOMONBIY APSONASI"

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ABSTRACT

Application of semantic types of adjectives, application of color, stick, condition, taste, scale, intermediate meaning, adjectives and adjectives.

Adjective is a set of words that express the type, quantity, quality of something. According to the lexical-semantic meaning of quality, quality and participation are divided into two types. They are divided into several types of meaning. The basic and artificial adjectives are divided into several semantic types, depending on what sign the breed expresses.

1. Color (white, black, red)
2. Stick (good, bad, soft)
3. Status (young, clean, old)
4. Characteristics of humans and animals (love, fear)
5. Taste (delicious, sweetheart)
6. Ancient people (pure, high)
7. Scale, in the sense of distance (wide, narrow, far, near)
8. Place, time (at home, at school, in the summer)
9. Similarity, in the sense of partnership (needle, camel, classmate)
10. That he has something to be understood from the basis (intelligent, knowledgeable, fruitful)
11. Lack of what is meant by the basis (innocent, innocent, careless) [1:108]

In this article, we will look at the application of adjectives in the sense of color.

For example:

An arrow-colored yellow woolen cloak with a buttoned collar and a black felt hat on his head was spread out like an eagle's wings, ready to fly. [2:3]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: yellow, black

The tall young man was exhausted and was leading two black horses by the reins. [2:5]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: black

Sheikh Murad was sitting on an ice horse, wearing a brown coat, with an arrow turban, a white beard, and a slight bow. [2:5]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: brown, white

He wore a steel shield with a gold-embroidered saddle on his forehead, a black sword on his forehead, a bow and arrow on his shoulder, a black cloak, a black cap, and a beard. [2:10]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: black

The keraga of the house is as red as the blood of the nose, the blues are yellow, the felt rings are as white as snow. [2:15]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: yellow, red, white, blue

His beard, his mustache, were black, and his yellow hair was stained with blood. [2:16]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: black, yellow

Those who came to the meeting were wearing black hats. [2:20]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: black

Ubaydulla biy looked at his friend's tired, sunburned, darkened face:

All right, listen, he said. [2:25]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: darkened, sunburned

When the khan's fox's yellow teeth appeared between his long black mustaches, the girl leaned back against the wall, saying, "I'm chewing."

- "Father, father of water, where are you?" [2:50]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: yellow, black

Katinek Suwpi then returned to the kitchen and poured yellow celery into the prepared chicken broth. [2:60]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: yellow

Yellow sparrows and swallows compete with the nightingale. [2:75]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: yellow

The girl in the red dress was actually the daughter of Aygara Biy. [2:80]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: red

In the corner of his eye he saw a man in a red jacket. [2:88]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: red

The sun is shining in the sky, and the vast expanses of the Aryan Kingdom stand like a plant seen in the spring, stretching them out with their blue robes that they wear in the summer. [2:143]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: blue

Mulberry groves with green leaves and green grass covered with carpets across the wide fields cheered up the roads. [2:150]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: green

Maman Biy spoke with joy, looking at the green wheat with a special love, like a blue velvet. [2:155]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: green, blue

It is the most beautiful place in the shady, mirrored village, with beautiful greenery. [2:160]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: greenery

Even our ancestors did not live in such stone-walled, stone-clad castle with green grass on the stone. [2:176]

Here, the color-defining qualities are: green

Adjectives are often used in works of art. The semantic types of quality play an important role in enhancing the essence of the work. T.Kayipbergenov widely used adjectives in his works. In the play, types of adjectives are used to denote color, condition, space. In this play, the qualities of a particular color are widely used in the exaggeration of nature, in the style of metaphor, in the style of comparison, in the style of metonymy.

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